

Telemedicine Solutions for Chronic Care Management: Advancing Patient Care in 2025

*Author: Seyed Farzad Mirmiran*¹, Business & Academic
Researcher, CEU university; DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.14032187

Executive Summary:

Chronic diseases account for a significant portion of healthcare costs and present ongoing challenges for patient care and engagement. In 2025, telemedicine is revolutionizing chronic care management, providing scalable solutions for long-term, continuous care that aligns with patients' needs and lifestyles. This white paper outlines the role of telemedicine in improving outcomes for chronic conditions, addresses implementation strategies, and showcases how healthcare providers can utilize telemedicine to transform chronic disease management effectively and efficiently.

¹ - Senior Academic & Business Researcher at CEU University;

([Dr.Seyed Farzad Mirmiran \(gumroad.com\)](https://www.gumroad.com/Dr.SeyedFarzadMirmiran)) or;
<https://drmirmiran.gumroad.com/> & drmirmiran@yahoo.com)